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LEGAL PROTECTION OF CHILDREN IN THE REPUBLIC OF BULGARIA AFTER THE DEMOCRATIC TRANSITION TOWARDS THE RULE OF LAW

The subject matter of this scientific paper is the new arrangement of children's legal protection in the Bulgarian legislation and juridical practice after 1989. Special attention is given to the international legal acts, such as the UN Convention on children's rights, which was ratified and transposed into the Bulgarian legislation. Another significant issue is the institutional support for children's rights and establishment of the Agency for Children's Rights Protection, as a new public institution at the national level. In this regard, the author examines the legal practice of the Agency for Children's Rights Protection Agency. The paper also provides an overview of the necessary legislative and institutional changes, aimed at improving the protection of children's rights and providing opportunities for personal development, social integration and defending human dignity of children as an important and highly vulnerable category of civil society.

Keywords: political transition, democracy, political pluralism, rule of law, human rights, dignity, legal regulations, transparency, state institutions' accountability, children's rights, Agency for Children's Rights Protection, budget policies, administrative procedures, judicial practice.

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PRAVNA ZAŠTITA DECE U REPUBLICI BUGARSKOJ NAKON DEMOKRATSKE TRANZICIJE KA VLADAVINI PRAVA

Predmet ovog naučnog rada je novo uređenje pravne zaštite dece u bugarskom zakonodavstvu i sudskoj praksi nakon 1989. godine. Posebna pažnja je posvećena međunarodnim pravnim aktima, kao što je Konvencija UN o pravima deteta, koja je ratifikovana i transponovana u bugarsko zakonodavstvo. Još jedno značajno pitanje je institucionalna podrška pravima deteta i uspostavljanje Agencije za zaštitu prava deteta, kao nove javne institucije na nacionalnom nivou. U tom kontekstu, autor razmatra praksu Agencije za zaštitu prava deteta. Rad takođe daje pregled neophodnih zakonskih i institucionalnih promena, usmerenih na poboljšanje zaštite prava deteta i pružanje mogućnosti za lični razvoj, socijalnu integraciju i odbranu ljudskog dostojanstva dece kao važne i veoma ranjive kategorije civilnog društva.

Ključne reči: politička tranzicija, demokratija, politički pluralizam, vladavina prava, ljudska prava, dostojanstvo, pravni propisi, transparentnost, odgovornost državnih institucija, prava deteta, Agencija za zaštitu prava deteta, budžetske politike, upravni postupci, sudska praksa.